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Edited by:
Tünde Alapi
Róbert Berkecz
István Ilisz

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*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and
Environmental Protection*

SMOKING HABITS AND CADMIUM AS BIOMARKER AMONG LUNG CANCER
FEMALE PATIENTS IN VOJVODINA

Nataša Milošević¹, Maja Milanović¹, Sanja Bijelović^{1,2}, Danica Sazdanić Velikić^{1,3},
Jovana Drljača¹, Nataša Milić¹, Jan Sudji^{1,4}, Mirka Lukić Sarkanović^{1,5}, Ljilja
Torović^{1,2}, Milorad Španović^{1,4}

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

²Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

³Institute for pulmonary diseases of Vojvodina, Clinic for pulmonary oncology, Sremska
Kamenica, Serbia

⁴Institute of Occupational Health of Novi Sad, Novi Sad

⁵University Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Clinic for anesthesiology, intensive therapy and
pain therapy, Novi Sad, Serbia

e-mail: natasa.milosevic@mf.uns.ac.rs

Introduction

Lung cancer is the second most common cancer (after breast cancer) in women and by far the leading cause of cancer death. According to the American Cancer Society there is chance of 1 in 17 women to be affected by lung cancer in their lifetime, with higher risk for the smokers.

Experimental

In this study 21 women (44-83 years old) with inoperable IIIB and IV stadium of lung carcinoma, diagnosed in the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Serbia were enrolled. All the women were asked to fulfil a questionnaire regarding their smoking habits. Their morning urine samples were collected and analysed by ICP-MS for the presence of cadmium (Cd) in the urine samples.

Results and discussion

More than half of the patients, 52.38% (11/21) enrolled in this study were diagnosed with adenocarcinoma, 23.81% (5/21) had squamous lung carcinoma while 14.28% (3/21) were discovered to have neuroendocrine lung carcinoma and 9.52% (2/21) were identified with small cell lung carcinoma. All of them were or still are heavy smokers who had or have been smoking cigarettes actively on daily basis. They had started to smoke on average at the age of 20 years (the youngest at the age of 12), and have been smoking for almost 41 year on average (15-56 years of smoking experience). Out of nine who have reported that had stopped smoking, only three had quitted smoking for 1 year or longer. Most of them 85.71% (18/21) origin from a family with smokers. On average, they had or have been smoking approximately a pack of cigarettes (18.8 cigarettes a day). In this study Cd was detected in 80.95% (17/21) of samples. All women with neuroendocrine lung carcinoma and small cell lung carcinoma had Cd in their morning urine samples.

Conclusion

To the best of authors knowledge such study has not been performed in Western Balkan Region. The obtained results confirmed that Cd is omnipresent in urine of women with lung cancer and that exposure to Cd is associated with smoking.

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**SMOKING HABITS, CADMIUM EXPOSURE AND VULNERABILITY TO
CHEMICALS OF LUNG ADENOCARCINOMA MALE PATIENTS IN VOJVODINA**

**Maja Milanović¹, Nataša Milošević¹, Danica Sazdanić Velikić^{1,2}, Jovana Drljača¹, Sanja
Bijelović^{1,3}, Jan Sudji^{1,4}, Mirjana Ševo², Danijela Lukić³, Nataša Milić¹**

¹*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*Institute for pulmonary diseases of Vojvodina, Clinic for pulmonary oncology, Sremska
Kamenica, Serbia*

³*Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia*

⁴*Institute of Occupational Health Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia*

email: maja.milanovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

Introduction

The American Cancer Society estimates that each year, more people die of lung cancer than of colon, breast, and prostate cancers combined. It is evaluated that 87% lung cancers are non-small cell cases, out of which 52% are adenocarcinoma. During their lifetime, 1 in 15 men will be affected by lung cancer and the risk for the smokers is higher.

Experimental

In this research 28 male patients (39-77 years old) with inoperable IIIB and IV stadium of adenocarcinoma, diagnosed in the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Serbia were enrolled. The patients were asked to fulfil questionnaire regarding their exposure to chemicals during lifetime and their smoking habits. The presence of cadmium (Cd) was determined by ICP-MS in their morning urine samples.

Results and discussion

More than one third of the included patients, 35.71% (10/28) had been exposed to various chemicals during their education or in their free time, while 32.14% (9/28) have been exposed to chemicals professionally. The list of chemicals includes ammonia, mineral acids, pesticides, petroleum products, paints, varnishes, glues and organic solvents. Only 2 of them have not been smoking during their lifetime, while 92.86% (26/28) reported that have been or had been heavy cigarette smokers who had started to smoke on average at the age of 19.6 years. As ex-smokers were registered 57.14% (16/28) patients who had been smoking on average for 38 years 25.83 cigarettes a day. Active smokers who were included in this study 35.71% (10/28), smoke on average 29.17 cigarettes daily. Cd was detected in 53.57% (15/28) of total urine samples, 62.50% (10/16) of ex-smokers versus 40.00% (4/10) active smokers.

Conclusion

In this study for the first time, the exposure to chemicals and smoking habits among lung adenocarcinoma male patients in Western Balkan Region are reported.

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